

Deliverable D7.6.

REQUIREMENTS FOR COMMUNICATION WITH POLICY MAKERS & PUBLIC BODIES

Deliverable report

Deliverable No.	D7.6	Work Package No.	WP7	Task/s No.	Tasks 7.4
Work Package Title	REQUIREMENTS FOR COMMUNICATION WITH POLICY MAKERS & PUBLIC BODIES				
Linked Task/s Title	Requirements for Communication with policy makers & public bodies.				
Status		Final			
Dissemination level	PU	PU-Public			
Due date deliverable	2021-11-30	Submission date	2021-11-30		
Deliverable version	DEQ_D7.6_ANE_V1.1_202111.30.doc				

Document Contributors

Deliverable responsible	ANEFA	
Contributors	Organisation	
CÉSAR LUACES FRADES	ANEFA	
LORENA VILADÉS SANTOS	ANEFA	
PAULO ROMERO MARTÍNEZ	ANEFA	
Reviewers	Organisation	
Leire Martiarena	ZABALA	
Lucía Eguillor	ZABALA	

Document History

Version	Date	Comment
1.0	2021-10-14	First version
1.1	2021-29-11	Second version

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List of Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	DESCRIPTION
CA	Consortium Agreement
DoA	Description of Action
DCEP	Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan
EB	Exploitation Board
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
IQS	Intelligent Quarrying System
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MoM	Minutes of Meetings
PCo	Project Coordinator
RP	Reporting Period
RM	Raw Materials
WP	Work Package

1 Executive Summary

This document defines the requirements for communication with policy makers & public bodies of the DIGIECOQUARRY project that will be needed for the elaboration of the Communications with policy makers plan.

This deliverable will be completed in month 20 (D7.7) with the Communications with policy makers plan and in months 36 (D7.8) and 48 (D7.9) with the Evaluation report for Communications with policy makers.

It provides meaningful information regarding the requirements for communication with policy makers & public bodies; It includes the structure of the deliverable as well as its scope, its relation to other tasks, activities and deliverables and the first description of the procedures for communication with policy makers.

The different objectives of the communication with policy makers & public bodies are explained.

The deliverable defines the partners' requirements & role in the communication with policy makers & public bodies strategy.

It develops the different categories of policy makers, regulators & public bodies at international, EU, National, Regional & Local levels.

The reference to Dissemination and Communication materials and tools is made to WP9 materials. The requirements for communication and dissemination materials and tools and for meetings and workshops are also defined.

The deliverable describes the context, governance, organisation and structure as well as ethics, it explains that the requirements that will be applied for the better regulation approach are those defined by the European Commission and refers to Green Deal & 2030 climate framework, EU principles for sustainable raw materials, UN Sustainable Development Goals, EU Digital Policies and Health & Safety.

2 Introduction

2.1 The DigiEcoQuarry project

DIGIECOQUARRY is a Horizon 2020 project aiming to design, develop and validate in 5 pilot environments an Innovative Quarrying System (IQS) comprising sensors, processes, tools and methods for data capture, processing and sharing to provide integrated, digitalised, automatic and real-time process control for aggregates quarries.

The DIGIECOQUARRY consortium will combine the latest researched and advanced technologies applied to quarry operation together with the integration of selected innovative digital solutions to boost the capacity of the aggregates industry, to enhance Health & Safety conditions for workers, to improve the Process and Efficiency of the aggregates extractive sites, to maximise Sustainability and Resource Efficiency in the quarry operations and to foster Social Acceptance.

Figure 1. DIGIECOQUARRY's concept.

2.2 Scope of the deliverable

This report, titled ‘**D7.6: Requirements for communication with policy makers & public bodies**’, aims to determine the framework in which the designed strategy that will be delivered in the corresponding Plan, with actions and activities implemented for communication and interaction with public policies, under the DIGIECOQUARRY project, will maximise the project’s visibility and impact.

This deliverable has been developed under WP7 Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policy makers aiming to define and implement one-way and two-way communication actions with policy makers.

The project Task 7.4 Requirements for Communication with policy makers & public bodies is led by ANEFA and the partners involved are MUL, CHAL, UPM-AI, DGA, FAEN, ASO, MIN, ZAB. This task will define fair & transparent communication requirements, in line with WP9.

This Task 7.4 is subdivided in:

- ST7.4.1. Definition of legal requirements applicable to aggregates quarries. Due to the complexity to deal with regional and national specificities, European requirements will be taken as a reference. The national, regional and local requirements will only be considered for each pilot site. The IQS platform will have the possibility to establish particular threshold values for each site as reference for the indicators delivered by the system.
- ST7.4.2. Actions & proposals for a sustainable management of environment protection, climate change prevention and ecological transition and also actions & proposals to optimise the management of the production process to increase efficiency and productivity, including Health & Safety and social acceptance. In terms of the process, each one of the phases will be analysed to propose specific tools for its improvement.
- ST7.4.3. Definition of indicators and the trends and levels to be achieved in each one, covering the following criteria: (1) Security of supply for the satisfaction of the demand of the product in a near, medium or distant environment; (2) Efficient use of natural resources; (3) Application of measures to promote and improve the safety and health of workers; (4) Contribution to the economic development of the community; (5) Contribution to the social development of the community; (6) Rehabilitation of the affected natural space; (7) Application of the best techniques available in integrated pollution prevention and control and waste management.

This Task is also linked with:

- T7.5 Interaction with local, national and international Policy makers, that addresses the implementation and follow-up of the requirements defined in T7.4 in line with the Communication strategy. To that end, a specific plan will be delivered to reach policy makers and other relevant public bodies or stakeholders related to the aggregates sector. This plan will be tackled at local and national levels (partners’ countries) but also EU level and beyond, counting with relevant partners in South Africa and Colombia to achieve worldwide influence.
- &
- O07 To foster social acceptance of the quarrying sector by introducing novel participatory processes and engagement actions with local communities and policy makers to achieve the Social License to Operate (SLO) and improve public acceptance and trust of the new quarrying technologies.

In that sense, solid guidelines to communicate with policy makers and public bodies are to be delivered, in line with international principles (i.e. the 2030 climate framework, Sustainable Development Goals and EU Green Deal), in clause 9.

2.3 Feeding RMIS and EURMKB

- Close cooperation with policy makers to feed RMIS and EURMKB is expected within WP8, together with network and clustering activities.

2.4 Procedures for communication with policy makers

Communication activities with policy makers and public bodies will be performed by periodical videoconferences meetings, webinars, and later on, face to face meetings in workshops, conferences or seminars. Also it can be used the social media could be used as LinkedIn making working groups with other Mining DGs, Mining engineers association and experts groups to work in different specialisations.

2.5 Relation to other activities and deliverables

The communication with policy makers & public bodies will be developed in close contact and coordination with the other Tasks of WP7 and with the whole WP8 and WP9.

Figure 2. Relationship between WPs.

The requirements for communication with policy makers & public bodies will be fed by all the DIGIECOQUARRY project deliverables. But they will have a very close relationship with:

WP6

- D6.6 Overall assessment of results achieved and KPI analysis.

WP7

- D7.1 Context narrative, Social risk matrix and Stakeholder Mapping.
- D7.2 Social Risk Analysis.
- D7.3 Communications and Social Awareness plan.
- D7.4 CES.
- D7.5 SLO.

WP8

- D8.1 Clustering plan.

- D8.2 Protocols to cooperate with RMIS and EURMKB.
- D8.3 & D8.4 Report on interactions with other organisations, projects and the IAB.

WP9

- D9.1 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan.
- D9.2 DIGIECOQUARRY's website.
- D9.3 & D9.5 & D9.8 Dissemination and Communication Materials.

WP10

- D10.3 & 10.7 & 10.9 Risk management and contingency plan.

2.6 Structure of the deliverable

With the above in mind, the “requirements for communication with policy makers & public bodies” is structured as follows:

Section 1 – Executive summary.

Section 2 – Introduction. Provides meaningful information regarding the requirements for communication with policy makers & public bodies; It includes the structure of the deliverable as well as its scope, its relation to other tasks, activities and deliverables and the first description of the procedures for communication with policy makers.

Section 3 – Objectives. Explains the different objectives of the communication with policy makers & public bodies.

Section 4 – Target groups. Explains the partners' requirements & role in the communication with policy makers & public bodies strategy.

Section 5 – Mapping of policy makers, public bodies, stakeholders and target groups. Develops the different categories of policy makers, regulators & public bodies at international, EU, National, Regional & Local levels.

Section 6 – Dissemination and Communication materials and tools. Refers to WP9 materials, defines the requirements for communication and dissemination materials and tools and for meetings and workshops.

Section 7 – Ethical requirements for Communication. Describes the context, governance, organisation and structure as well as ethics.

Section 8 – General better regulation requirements. Explains that the requirements that will be applied for the better regulation approach are those defined by the European Commission.

Section 9 – Specific political & regulatory framework for Communication. Refers to Green Deal & 2030 climate framework, EU principles for sustainable raw materials, UN Sustainable Development Goals, EU Digital Policies and Health & Safety.

Section 10 – KPIs. Refers to D7.7 (M20).

Section 11 – Timetable. Refers to D7.7 (M20).

Section 12 – Conclusions. Summarises the conclusions of this deliverable.

The **Annexes** include, among other:

- The EU requirements on communication and dissemination of results.
- The list of members of UEPG, GAIN and FIPA.
- The list of representations with policy makers of ANEFA

3 Objectives

DIGIECOQUARRY project has the following general objectives in terms of communication with policy makers & public bodies:

- To have a multidisciplinary approach to the origin and development of public policies to exchange, learn and dialogue with policy makers & public bodies, aimed at providing the DIGIECOQUARRY vision, knowledge and tools to understand how the public policies are shaped, how to interact in a liquid relational ecosystem and how to optimise their performance in the current context of change and uncertainty.
- To provide strategic keys to optimise the interaction of DIGIECOQUARRY project with political, social and institutional stakeholders.
- To help to maximise analytical capacity and understanding of the new processes of shaping opinion, decision-making and the exercise of power, linked with DIGIECOQUARRY project.
- To provide DIGIECOQUARRY partners with tools and techniques that enable them to successfully face change processes in the development of public policies, including those that pose challenges or threats to the future of digitalisation.
- To establish dynamics for planning, developing and evaluating public affairs plans that respond to the new digitalisation challenges and have an impact on the DIGIECOQUARRY project.
- To enhance the development of leadership and strategic management skills in the field of public affairs for DIGIECOQUARRY partners.

More precisely, DIGIECOQUARRY project communication with policy makers & public bodies will tackle the following complementary objectives described in Figure 3.

Figure 3. DIGIECOQUARRY's main objectives of the communication with PM & PB.

3.1 Contribute to law-making and the improvement of legislation

3.1.1 Commission & other policy makers initiatives

Contribute to public consultations and give feedback on policy makers and public bodies initiatives during policy making, by telling how existing laws could be improved.

3.1.2 Make suggestions to improve laws & regulations

Tell the policy makers and public bodies how regulatory burden could be reduced and how existing laws could be improved and made more effective.

3.2 Contribute to new policies, initiatives and roadmaps for Raw Materials

Provide strong evidence to establish new policies, initiatives and roadmaps for Raw Materials, based on DIGIECOQUARRY project solutions.

3.3 Alignment of public policies with emerging innovative mining systems

A plan to communicate to policy makers on alignment of public policies with emerging innovative mining systems. (...) the importance of the targeted RM for the EU economy has to be duly demonstrated in the proposal and will be the content of D7.7.

3.4 Connection with other EU / national initiatives, projects, platforms and networks

This action will be dedicated to reaching out and connecting with other EU as well as national initiatives, projects, platforms and networks related to “Secure System Design” and Industrial Security. This will include intra and extra project clustering (within consortium members and outside consortium partners). Thus, relevant agents will be identified in two areas:

[1] **Public bodies** (agents with competences in policy making in the quarrying sector, to be reached in WP7, &

[2] **Platforms and associations** from the mining/quarrying sector and/or linked with it, (to be reached in WP8); in order to create synergies and an International Contact Network to help paving the way towards the digital quarries of the future.

This will be linked to the overall Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation strategy in WP9 (D9.1).

EURMKB is a database that is part of the EIP on Raw Materials. Its aim is to be a one-stop-shop for all information on RM in the EU. DIGIECOQUARRY will contribute to collect, store, maintain, upgrade, analyse, and disseminate information on the RM and also feed from it. This knowledge base will serve industry and policy makers as a valuable source.

3.5 International cooperation

Pro-active international cooperation strategy of the EU at bi/multilateral level, promoting synergies with countries such as USA, Japan, Australia, Canada, Latin America and African Union across the different areas in the EIP.

Cooperation across the EU. This is key for DIGIECOQUARRY and will be ensured by implementing a sound Dissemination strategy (including a Clustering plan) and Communication strategy (which will involve policy makers).

Cooperation out of EU. DIGIECOQUARRY is very well placed for an effective cooperation action outside EU, thanks to:

- **MINTEK** (South Africa) and **ASOGRAVAS** (Colombia), as partners of the project, will facilitate cooperation with Africa and specially with LATAM.
- The IAB is composed by very relevant international bodies (i.e. **GAIN**) with presence in the five continents and more specifically in the USA, Japan, Australia, Canada and LATAM. The European Aggregates Association – **UEPG**¹ has 26 member association in Europe, Turkey and Israel. The membership of UEPG is detailed in Annex II.
- One of the members of the International Advisory Network is GAIN. **GAIN**² is the acronym of the **Global Aggregates Information Network**. It is an entirely voluntary network of the major regional aggregates associations of the world. It has no commercial interests and vigorously enforces an anti-trust policy. The purpose of GAIN is to openly share experiences and industry best practices in the interests of promoting the greater sustainability and performance of the aggregates industry globally. Its meetings show that the challenges experienced by the industry in various parts of the world are remarkably similar, yet different regions can have surprisingly differing solutions. Consequently, there are valuable “gems of wisdom” experiences and best practices to be exchanged.

Figure 4. DIGIECOQUARRY’s main objectives of the communication with PM & PB.

The membership of GAIN is detailed in Annex III.

1 <https://uepg.eu>

2 <https://www.gain.ie>

The PCo of DIGIECOQUARRY is a permanent member of the Board of GAIN.

- **Federación Iberoamericana de Productores de Áridos – FIPA³**: The PCo of DIGIECOQUARRY is the Director General and the General Secretary of ASOGRAVAS has the same post in this Iberoamerican Federation.

The membership of FIPA is detailed in Annex IV.

3.6 Solution of legislative barriers/obstacles

- Among the different legislative barriers and obstacles identified in the project, could appear those related with:
 - **Environmental Regulations** such as:
 - **Water**: Minimum requirements for water reuse; Environmental quality standards applicable to surface water; EU water resources protection plan; Addressing water scarcity and droughts in the EU; Flood-risk management in the EU; Drinking water — essential quality standards; Good-quality water in Europe (EU Water Directive); Protection of groundwater against pollution; Drinking water — essential quality standards.
 - **Environmental responsibility**: The polluter-pays principle and environmental liability; Assessing environmentally sustainable investments.
 - **Agriculture & land-useplanning**: Landfill of waste; Carbon dioxide capture and storage.
 - **Tackling climate change**: European Climate Law; Programme for the environment and climate action (LIFE) (2021-2027).
 - **EU climate change policy**: Moving towards a low-carbon economy in 2050; EU policy framework for climate and energy (2020 to 2030).
 - **Air**: Cleaner air for Europe; Carbon dioxide capture and storage; National emission limits for certain air pollutants; EU rules on national emissions of certain atmospheric pollutants.
 - **Chemicals**: European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) — how the EU regulates chemicals.
 - **Nature & biodiversity**: Conservation of wild birds; Protecting biodiversity from invasive alien species; Convention on the conservation of migratory species of wild animals — Bonn Convention; Convention on Biological Diversity; Programme for the environment and climate action (LIFE) (2021-2027); Protecting Europe’s biodiversity (Natura 2000).
 - **Noise**: Noise emission by equipment used outdoors; Assessment and management of environmental noise; Motor vehicles with trailers: permissible sound level.
 - **Soil & forests**: Landfill of waste; Combatting deforestation.
 - **Waste**: Landfill of waste; Management of waste from extractive industries; EU waste management law; Recycling.

³ www.fiparidos.com

- **Industry & pollution:** Industrial emissions; European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (E-PRTR)
- **Environmental controls & assessments:** Integration of environmental aspects into European standardisation; Assessment of the effects of projects on the environment (EIA); EU biodiversity strategy for 2030; The EU's infrastructure for spatial information (Inspire); The polluter-pays principle and environmental liability; Reliable benchmarking of environmental performance; Better environmental performance: European eco-management and audit scheme (EMAS); The precautionary principle; Assessment of the certain effects of plans and programmes on the environment (SEA).
- o **Health and Safety** regulations such as Directive 89/391/EEC, the so-called occupational safety and health (OSH) "Framework Directive" and its daughter Directives, in particular:
 - Mineral-extracting industries (Directive 92/104/EEC).
 - Mineral-extracting industries through drilling (Directive 92/91/EEC).
 - Workplace requirements (Directive 89/654/EEC).
 - Work equipment (Directive 2009/104/EC).
 - Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) (Directive 89/656/EEC).
 - Safety and/or health signs at work (Directive 92/58/EEC).
 - Display screen equipment (Directive 90/270/EEC).
 - Risks related to chemical agents at work (Directive 98/24/EC).
 - Exposure to carcinogens or mutagens at work (Directive 2004/37/EC).
 - Exposure to asbestos at work (Directive 2009/148/EC).
 - Risks from explosive atmospheres (Directive 1999/92/EC).
 - Risks arising from vibration (Directive 2002/44/EC).
 - Risks arising from noise (Directive 2003/10/EC).
- All this regulation can be an advantage for the project, as DIGIECOQUARRY technology is especially conceived to tackle environmental and H&S challenges within the quarrying sector, increasing the market size and acceptance within the EU.

3.7 Contribution to standardisation

A set of standards have been identified and considered at project proposal stage.

Additionally, partners will act as liaison with main standardisation bodies and policy makers around Europe and beyond, to lay the basis for future standards.

3.8 Contribution to regulatory compliance

The way to ensure a smooth introduction of the innovative solutions developed in the project and the associated new collaborative environments to achieve the sustainable quarry & mining industries and RM

targets is through the alignment of the project with the current legislation. DIGIECOQUARRY will comply with current standards/regulation at international level, or national when there are no global guidelines.

Also, WPs 7 and 8 will need hand-in-hand working with relevant actors and policy makers related with standardisation and regulation bodies (e.g. ANEFA and UEPG (represented in the IAB), provides reference standards for the aggregates sector at EU level), such as EN 15804, UNE 22480:2019, UNE 22470:2019, ISO/CD TR 14035 Environmental technology verification — ETV and EN 15805 standard for environmental product declaration (EPD). The EPD is connected to European environmental database (Soda4LCA) and also other external open source databases (i.e. Ecoinvent, which is a LCA database) could be used.

Other interoperability standards (e.g. for IT platforms, edge computing and interoperability: platform connectors in public clouds like AWS, OneM2M, ETSI) and the selection and creation of Common Information Models (CIMs) for data sharing shall foster adoption and replicability of DIGIECOQUARRY's solutions.

3.9 Raise awareness on the aggregates industry

Raise awareness on the aggregates industry and reinforcing the messages from the quarrying sector, and delivering improved performance, H&S, social and environmental indicators.

3.10 Interaction between scale experimentation and policy making

DEQ is developing a communication protocol between all industry stakeholders (IQS) to set up a complete layer from the start of the exploitation of the material to the elaboration of industry/company policies.

Focusing on the operational level of sites, it generates the data and information necessary to define the mission and vision of companies, policy makers and public bodies. As will be demonstrated by conducting the 5 pilots.

3.11 Use of EU dissemination channels

DIGIECOQUARRY's communication and dissemination plan will take advantage of the following EU dissemination channels that could be used during the project:

- EU-OSHA.
- CEDEFOP. The European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training brings together policy-makers, social partners, researchers and practitioners to share ideas and debate the best ways to improve vocational education and training policies.
- European Enterprise Network (EEN). The EEN is an EU network of around 600 business support organizations from more than 60 countries, including chambers of commerce and industry, technology centres, research institutes and development agencies.
- CORDIS (Community Research and Development Information Service) WIRE. CORDIS WIRE is a CORDIS online service that helps research and business community to promote projects' activities by publishing news and events on CORDIS
- EU Info-days, workshops and conferences.

4 Partners' requirements & role in the communication with policy makers & public bodies strategy

4.1 Required skills & requirements

DIGIECOQUARRY partners does not need a particular set of skills to participate in the project's strategy for communication with policy makers & public bodies.

All the preparation of materials and messages for the communication with policy makers & public bodies will be coordinated and prepared by ANEFA as PCo. The PCo has 27 years of experience in the communication with policy makers & public bodies at all levels (EU / National / Regional / Local). He also has an Esade Business School title on Public Agenda Management: "*Power and Counterpower: A multidisciplinary approach to the origin and development of public policies, for general manager training*" focused in the development of corporate strategy, participation in the definition of public policies and relations with the administration and other stakeholders in the public and private sector.

DIGIECOQUARRY partners and their strategic positioning in Europe (and also ASO and MINTEK in Colombia and South Africa, respectively) count with vast capacities to influence the target communities and will act as multipliers.

The D7.7 Communications with policy makers plan will include advise, recommendations, protocols and tools for all of the partners, to help to develop the following skills:

- To identify, generate and optimise spaces for collaboration between the public and private sectors in order to increase the relational capital of the organisation.
- To manage successful negotiation processes in contexts of multipolarity, asymmetries and multiplicity of actors.
- To strengthen their capacities to participate and influence new governance processes (multilevel, with new dynamics of democratic participation, smart regulation, intersectoral collaboration).
- To learn about new mechanisms for defining strategies for building and/or transforming opinion (reputation, negotiation and framing).
- To deepen the concept of "strategic intelligence": identify trends and tools in advocacy and/or public affairs (data, grassroots, crowd power).

4.2 Role of DEQ partners with policy makers and ongoing initiatives

Some partners have already extensive policy maker knowledge and experience, and also thanks to their presence in key initiatives, i.e. Minerals Policy Guidance for Europe (MIN-GUIDE), Strategic Dialogue on Sustainable RM for Europe (STRADE) and Sustainable aggregates planning in South East Europe (SNAP SEE) and policy advisory committees, they will establish significant connections with specific policy maker entities to comply with existing policies and define new roadmaps or policy/regulatory issues within the aggregates/mining sector.

4.2.1 The coordinator of the ANEFA

ANEFA, the PCo is an entrepreneur association and is a policy maker by definition. From this excellent position, ANEFA is very well placed to coordinate the approach to other policy makers and public bodies around the Aggregates Industry. So ANEFA is the responsible for the communication with policy makers.

ANEFA is involved in the development of key roadmaps in the sector:

- [1] Plan for sectoral technological and organisational improvements 2011-2020 (FEDER).
- [2] Strategic plan of the aggregates sector 2012-2025.
- [3] Strategic plan of the aggregates sector Áridos2030.
- [4] Comprehensive Strategic Program for the Improvement of Environmental Management of SMEs in the Aggregates Sector.
- [5] UEPG Roadmap 2030.

ANEFA is also a member of a number of National and European policy makers and public bodies: Spanish Mining Safety Commission, EC RM Supply Group, EC Working Group on Explosives for Civil Uses, EC Strategic Coordination Group on Water, EC Sectoral Social Dialogue Committee for the Extractive Industries, etc. In Annex V all the representations of ANEFA are listed.

Figure 5. ANEFA's relationship map.

4.2.2 DGASTUR & FAEN

DGASTUR is a policy maker and a member of Mining Safety Commission of Asturias, Mining Safety Commission of Spain and Mining Coordination Group of Spanish Regions, as well as Vice presidency of The Central Mining

Rescue Brigade. DGASTUR is linked with Just Transition Regions and with the European Mining Regions Network.

The Asturian Energy Foundation – FAEN is attached to the Administration of the Principality of Asturias. FAEN has as members the Government of the Principality of Asturias, city councils, universities and companies and is a meeting point between the industrial sectors and policy makers. The object and purpose of the Foundation is to promote, carry out and develop any advisory, research, technological progress, services, awareness and training activities in the field of energy, environmental sustainability and others -directly or indirectly- related to them.

4.2.3 ASOGRAVAS

ASOGRAVAS, the Colombian Association of Producers of Stone Aggregates will be supporting the International cooperation with LATAM and with the Colombian Government. ASOGRAVAS lead the communication with national and local public authorities both proactively and preventively, to ensure an optimal legal environment that guarantees the continuity of existing operations and the opening of new production centres.

ASOGRAVAS also develop a strategy at the level of public and private entities to position the Association as a reference in the Colombian mining-industrial activity and to enhance the visibility and importance of the building materials sector in the national economic context.

4.2.4 MINTEK

MINTEK is South Africa’s national mineral research organisation and is one of the world’s leading technology organisations specialising in mineral processing, extractive metallurgy and related areas. MINTEK is a state owned science council which reports to the Minister of Mineral Resources.

MINTEK’s mandate is to serve the national interest through research, development and technology transfer, to promote mineral technology and to foster the establishment and expansion of industries in the field of minerals and products derived therefrom.

MINTEK will be supporting the International cooperation with South Africa.

4.2.5 ZABALA

ZABALA is a partner company with expertise in innovation ecosystems by the management and public financing of R&D&I projects. Thanks to this experience ZABALA closely collaborates with Universities, Technology and Research Centres, R&D Units, Investment Firms, Public Administrations, etc.

4.2.6 Universities

Montan University of Leoben, Madrid Polytechnical University and Chalmers University of Technology have close and permanent contacts with policy makers so they will collaborate in setting the basis for a good and efficient communication. They will engage the EU (and also international) scientific and industrial communities to raise awareness about the project and contribute to knowledge generation and sharing.

4.2.7 The other partners

Next Table summarises the role of the other partners in the communication with policy makers & public bodies:

PARTNERS	ROLE IN THE COMMUNICATION WITH PM & PB
Large companies and R&D: SANDVIK, METSO, MAXAM, AKKA, ROCTIM	Communication will focus on their local policy makers & public bodies.
SMEs: ITK, ARCO, MAESTRO, DH&P, ABAUT, APP, SIGMA	Deliver technical background for technical communication, when needed.
Quarries: VICAT, HANSON, HOLCIM, CSI, CIMPOR	Communication will focus on their local policy makers & public bodies as well as on their stakeholders.

Table 1. Dissemination Strategy per partner profile.

4.3 Consortium Members of the EU Transparency Register

Eleven of the DIGIECOQUARRY Consortium members are registered in the EU Transparency Register. This is a very relevant asset for the whole communication with policy makers & public bodies.

4.3.1 Trade and business associations

ANEFA, the project coordinator and responsible for communication with policy makers & public bodies is registered in the EU Transparency Register since 16/03/2016:

- ANEFA 573844521096-42 – Spain

4.3.2 Companies & groups

Seven partners of the Consortium are registered in the EU Transparency Register as companies & groups:

- AKKA Technologies (AKKA) 813844828231-47 – Belgium
- HeidelbergCement 81970148701-15 - Germany and Spain
- Holcim Ltd 225005818352-31 – Switzerland and Italy
- MAXAMCORP HOLDING (MAXAM) 283047124455-25 – Spain
- Metso Outotec Oyj 602839415178-51 – Finland
- Sandvik AB 480175226880-10 – Sweden
- Zabala Innovation Consulting, S.A. 759849612290-93 – Spain

4.3.3 Academic institutions

Three partners of the Consortium are registered in the EU Transparency Register as Academic institutions:

- Montanuniversitaet Leoben 442969023241-35 – Austria
- Universidad Politécnica de Madrid 555819220647-67 – Spain
- Chalmers University of Technology AB 644958024362-49 – Sweden

4.4 The role of the International Advisory Board

Remarkably, some member of the International Advisory Board – IAB have strong political connections. So they are very well placed to advise DIGIECOQUARRY Consortium on the best approach to manage a performant communication with policy makers & public bodies.

(i.e. IUCN provides linkages to EU institutions and other stakeholders in Brussels, UEPG positions are considered by EU decision makers, EGS provides the European Institutions with expert advice, etc.).

INTERNATIONAL ADVISORY BOARD					
Name of the member	Area of influence	Type of organisation	Added value	Link with other policy makers & public bodies	Partner in charge of the collaboration
Aggregates Business Europe – AGGB	EU	Media company	Can give advice on the content of the messages to be delivered to policy makers	Other media	ANEFA
European Agency for Safety and Health at Work – EU-OSHA	EU	European Official Agency Policy Maker	EU-OSHA has strong relationships with all its partners – the European Commission, the national focal points, the social partners, the campaign partners and its stakeholders	EU-OSHA has a national focal point in each Member State. They are typically the competent national authority for safety and health at work	ANEFA
European Aggregates Association – UEPG	EU	Entrepreneurs Organisation Policy Maker	Excellent contacts with all EU relevant policy makers	26 UEPG Member associations NEEIP associations Other European associations related with aggregates industry	ANEFA
Federal Association of Mineral Raw Materials E.V. – MIRO	Germany	Entrepreneurs Organisation Policy Maker	Excellent contacts with all German relevant policy makers	Other German associations related with aggregates industry	ANEFA
Geological Surveys of Europe – EuroGeoSurveys	EU	Policy Maker	EuroGeoSurveys members, the National Geological Surveys, are public sector institutions carrying out operations and research in the field of geosciences	38 National Geological Surveys and some regional Surveys in Europe	ANEFA UPM MUL
Global Aggregates Information Network – GAIN	Worldwide	Entrepreneurs Organisation Policy Maker	Excellent contacts with Worldwide Aggregates Associations	22 UEPG Member associations	ANEFA
International Union for Conservation of Nature – IUCN	Worldwide	Environmental NGO Policy Maker	Union composed of both government and civil society organisations	1,400 member organisations	ANEFA
Heidelberg Cement Group	Worldwide	Aggregates, Cement, Readymix concrete and Asphalt producer company	3,000 sites in 50 countries	Local & regional policy makers	ANEFA
CEMEX	Worldwide	Aggregates, Cement, Readymix concrete and Asphalt producer company	296 aggregates sites in 22 countries	Local & regional policy makers	ANEFA

Table 2. Members of the International Advisory Board.

4.5 The role of the other organisations supporting DIGIECOQUARRY

DIGIECOQUARRY received explicit support from other organisations, all of them policy makers or public bodies that will be a support for some actions of communication with other policy makers & public bodies.

ORGANISATIONS SUPPORTING DIGIECOQUARRY	
European Environment Agency (EU-Denmark)	Public Administrations
Spanish Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge (Spain)	
Ministry of Mines and Energy (Colombia)	
Instituto Geológico y Minero de España – IGME (Spain)	Accademia
AGH University of Science and Technology – Mining and Geoengineering Faculty (Poland)	
Associação Nacional da Indústria Extractiva e Transformadora – ANIET (Portugal)	Entrepreneurs Organisation
Associazione Nazionale Estrattori Produttori Lapidei ed Affini – ANEPLA (Italy)	
Confederación Española de Asociaciones de Fabricantes de Productos de Construcción – CEPCO (Spain)	
Confederación Española de Industrias Extractivas de Rocas y Minerales Industriales – COMINROC (Spain)	
Confederación Española de las Industrias de las Materias Primas Minerales – PRIMIGEA (Spain)	
Confederación Nacional de Empresarios de la Minería y Metalurgia – CONFEDEM (Spain)	
Committee for European Construction Equipment – CECE (EU-Brussels)	
Dirección General de Industria, Energía y Minas de la Comunidad de Madrid (Spain)	
EuroGypsum (EU-Brussels)	
European Asphalt Pavement Association – EAPA (EU-Brussels)	
European Cement Association – CEMBUREAU (EU-Brussels)	
Fachverband der Stein- und keramischen Industrie Österreich – FVSK (Austria)	
Federación Iberoamericana de Productores de Áridos – FIPA (Ibero-América)	
Gremi d'Àrids de Catalunya (Spain)	
Spanish Aggregates Federation – FdA (Spain)	
Union Nationale des Producteurs de Granulats – UNPG (France)	Environmental NGO
BIRDLIFE International (EU-Brussels)	
Fundación Tormes – E.B. (Spain)	Environmental Network
European Network for Sustainable Quarrying and Mining (EU-Brussels)	
Centro Tecnológico del Mármol, Piedra y Materiales (Spain)	Technological Centre
Laboratorio Oficial Madariaga – LOM (Spain)	

Table 3. Organisations supporting DIGIECOQUARRY.

5 Mapping of policy makers, public bodies, stakeholders and target groups

5.1 Policy makers, regulators & public bodies

5.1.1 Type of policy makers, regulators & public bodies

A classical classification of Policy makers, regulators & public bodies, applied to DIGIECOQUARRY project is based on the following categories:

Official policy makers & funding bodies

- **Parliament and other legislative & representative bodies** are of primary interest for the consortium given that they are responsible for setting the guidelines of the current and future mining policies that will affect the commercial feasibility of DIGIECOQUARRY.
- **Public Administrations and governments**, integrated by politicians and civil servants are of primary interest for the consortium given that they are responsible for setting the guidelines of the current and future mining policies that will affect the commercial feasibility of DIGIECOQUARRY.

Accademia & Researchers

- **Accademia and research stakeholders:** Academics, researchers and experts focused on advancing the scientific fields cross-cutting DIGIECOQUARRY.
- **Technological Centres.**
- **Standardisation bodies.**

Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates industries & Quarries

- **Entrepreneurs Organisations** with potential interest in the project's successful execution and results that will expand the project's scope towards new market opportunities to maximise its impact.
- **Corporate aggregates companies** with potential interest in the project's successful execution and results that will expand the project's scope towards new market opportunities to maximise its impact.

ICT industry

- **Technology providers.**

Construction sector and other clients

- **Construction associations.**

Citizens and civil society

- **Trade Unions.**
- **Environmental NGOs.**
- **Environmental Networks.**
- **Thinktanks.**

- International governance organisations.
- Other lobbyist entities.
- Other key General public stakeholders of DIGIECOQUARRY are non-governmental organizations, civil society groups or simply citizens, interested in the potential of DIGIECOQUARRY to address needs relevant to them.

Media, journalists and other groups

- Medias.

Figure 6. DIGIECOQUARRY's stakeholders.

5.1.2 International level

At worldwide level it is difficult to find policy makers, regulators & public bodies of interest and / or relationship with the aim of the project. Among them, the following are identified:

INTERNATIONAL POLICY MAKERS, REGULATORS & PUBLIC BODIES			
Name	Area of influence	Type of organisation	Link with the project
Ministry of Mines and Energy	Colombia	Public Administrations and governments	Supporter
United Nations Environmental Programme - UNEP	Worldwide	International governance organisations	None
Federación Iberoamericana de Productores de Áridos – FIPA	Ibero-América	Entrepreneurs Organisation	Supporter
Global Aggregates Information Network – GAIN	Worldwide		Member of the IAB
BIRDLIFE International	Worldwide	Environmental NGO	Supporter
International Union for Conservation of Nature – IUCN	Worldwide		Member of the IAB
Heidelberg Cement Group	Worldwide	Corporate aggregates companies	Member of the IAB
CEMEX	Worldwide		Member of the IAB

Table 4. International policy makers, regulators & public bodies.

5.1.3 EU level

At EU level a number of policy makers, regulators & public bodies are of interest and / or relationship with the aim of the project. Among them, the following are identified:

EU LEVEL POLICY MAKERS, REGULATORS & PUBLIC BODIES			
Name	Area of influence	Type of organisation	Link with the project
European Parliament	EU	Parliament and other legislative & representative bodies	None
Committee of Regions	EU		None
European Commission	EU	Public Administrations and governments	None
Council	EU		None
European Agency for Safety and Health at Work – EU-OSHA	EU		Member of the IAB
European Environment Agency - EEA	EU		Supporter
CEN and CENELEC	EU	Standardisation bodies	None
Geological Surveys of Europe – EuroGeoSurveys	EU	Thinktanks	Member of the IAB
EIT Raw Materials	EU		None
European Raw Materials Alliance – ERMA	EU	Entrepreneurs Organisations, ICT industry, Construction sector & other clients	None
European Aggregates Association – UEPG	EU		Member of the IAB
Committee for European Construction Equipment – CECE	EU		Supporter
EuroGypsum	EU		Supporter
European Asphalt Pavement Association – EAPA	EU		Supporter
European Cement Association – CEMBUREAU	EU		Supporter
EUROMINES	EU		Supporter (by ENSQM)
IMA Europe	EU		Supporter (by ENSQM)
Business Europe	EU		None
Non Energy Extractive Industry Panel – NEEIP	EU		None
Construction Products Europe – CPE	EU	None	
European Network for Sustainable Quarrying and Mining - ENSQM	EU	Environmental Network	Supporter
Aggregates Business Europe – AGGB	EU	Medias	Member of the IAB
IndustriAll	EU	Trade Unions	None
European Technology Platform on Sustainable Mineral Resources – ETP SMR)	EU	Other lobbyist entities	None

Table 5. EU level policy makers, regulators & public bodies.

5.1.4 National level

At National level a number of policy makers, regulators & public bodies are of interest and / or relationship with the aim of the project. Among them, the following are identified:

NATIONAL POLICY MAKERS, REGULATORS & PUBLIC BODIES			
Name	Area of influence	Type of organisation	Link with the project
Spanish Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge	Spain	Public Administrations and governments	Supporter
Other Ministries related with the extractive industry and with environmental issues	All EU countries		None
Ministry of Mines and Energy	Colombia		Supporter
Instituto Geológico y Minero de España – IGME	Spain		Supporter
Other Geological Surveys	All EU countries		Supporter (by EGS)
H&S national Bodies	All EU countries		None
Environmental national bodies	All EU countries		None
Standardisation national bodies	All EU countries	Standardisation bodies	None

Name	Area of influence	Type of organisation	Link with the project
AGH University of Science and Technology – Mining and Geoen지니어ing Faculty	Poland	Accademia	Supporter
Spanish Concrete Technical Platform – PTEH	Spain	Thinktanks	None
Associação Nacional da Indústria Extractiva e Transformadora – ANIET	Portugal	Entrepreneurs Organisations	Supporter
Associazione Nazionale Estrattori Produttori Lapidei ed Affini – ANEPLA	Italy		Supporter
Confederación Española de Asociaciones de Fabricantes de Productos de Construcción – CEPCO	Spain		Supporter
Asociación Nacional Española de Fabricantes de Hormigón Preparado - ANEFHOP	Spain		None
FEDIEX	Belgium		Supporter (by UEPG)
Mineral Products Association – MPA	UK		Supporter (by UEPG)
Spanish Confederation of Business Organisations – CEOE	Spain		None
Spanish Confederation of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises – CEPYME	Spain		None
Confederación Española de Industrias Extractivas de Rocas y Minerales Industriales – COMINROC	Spain		Supporter
Confederación Española de las Industrias de las Materias Primas Minerales – PRIMIGEA	Spain		Supporter
Confederación Nacional de Empresarios de la Minería y Metalurgia – CONFEDEM	Spain		Supporter
Fachverband der Stein- und keramischen Industrie Österreich – FVSK	Austria		Supporter
Gremi d'Àrids de Catalunya	Spain		Supporter
Spanish Aggregates Federation – FdA	Spain		Supporter
National Aggregates Associations	All EU countries		Supporter (by UEPG)
Union Nationale des Producteurs de Granulats – UNPG	France		Supporter
Fundación Tormes – E.B.	Spain	Environmental NGO	Supporter
Centro Tecnológico del Mármol, Piedra y Materiales	Spain	Technological Centre	Supporter
Laboratorio Oficial Madariaga – LOM	Spain		Supporter

Table 6. National level policy makers, regulators & public bodies.

5.1.5 Regional

At Regional level there is a number of policy makers, regulators & public bodies are of interest and / or relationship with the aim of the project. Among them, the following are identified:

REGIONAL POLICY MAKERS, REGULATORS & PUBLIC BODIES			
Name	Area of influence	Type of organisation	Link with the project
Dirección General de Industria, Energía y Minas de la Comunidad de Madrid	Spain	Public	Supporter
Other Administrations related with the extractive industry and with environmental issues	All EU regions	Administrations and governments	None

5.1.6 Local

At Local level the municipalities are the relevant policy makers, regulators & public bodies are of interest and / or relationship with the aim of the project.

5.2 Expected communication topics related with each profile

According with the categories defined in 5.1.1, the expected communication topics related with each profile are outlined in Table 7.

TARGET AUDIENCE	AIM	KEY MESSAGES
1. Official policy makers and funding bodies (Government, Regulatory agencies) at local, national and EU level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide strong evidence to establish new policies, initiatives and roadmaps for RM Interaction in WP7 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reinforcement of the Quarrying sector Improved performance, H&S, social and environmental indicators Raise awareness
2. Accademia. Researchers at universities, R&D centres or and Scientific societies in RM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhanced scientific knowledge R&D cooperation and promotion Clustering via WP8 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increase data available for research Main results shared in EURMKB and RMIS
3. Entrepreneur organisations. Aggregates industries & Quarries / RM <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholders and end users Material providers Industry associations and representatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Final users of DIGIECOQUARRY's result Commercial exploitation Project involvement Clustering via WP8 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Main results and experience from pilots Improved performance, H&S, social and environmental indicators Economic, investment & cost analysis Prospects of prolonging the productive life cycles of quarries
4. ICT industry <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technology providers Associations and representatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New range of services in Quarrying Commercial exploitation Open and flexible methodologies for interoperability of ICT tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Main results and experience reports from the pilots Available materials/services and knowledge generated
5. Construction sector and other clients	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote the development of new or improved products and services based on DIGIECOQUARRY results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved cost-efficient products, H&S, social & environmental KPIs Raise awareness
6. Citizens and civil society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> General awareness Social acceptance (SLO) Project involvement via WP7 	<p>In development in D 7.3 and 7.4:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Community Engagement Strategies Social Awareness plan Local engagement plan
7. Media, journalists and other groups (e.g., environment, energy, safety, NGOs, Consumer's organisations...)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> General awareness Improved perception of the extractive industry Trend setters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved performance, H&S, social and environmental indicators Available materials/services for communication purposes

Table 7. Target audience.

6 Dissemination and Communication materials and tools

6.1 Dissemination Assets

The Project's assets and outcomes that are here described, will be disseminated by all partners with a view to maximise the project's impact and visibility. This information is being conveyed in a meaningful way and tailored to each policy maker and public bodies group, in order to communicate and promote not only the DIGIECOQUARRY's results, but also its vision and aim.

- The **conceptual aspects** of the project, meaning the whole project concept, its innovative characteristics, its impact both on business and at social level, etc.
- The **technical achievements of the project** like the DIGIECOQUARRY IQS platform and the respective ICT infrastructure and needed toolkits. The assets of this category will be highly communicated once these tools are developed and thus a more detailed communication strategy will be contained in the next version of the DCEP.
- The **scientific knowledge** that derives from the project in the form of reports, scientific articles, etc.
- All the spectrum of the **project's activities**, like the four workshops that will be organized in the framework of DIGIECOQUARRY, the closing event, the participation in external events and every other action that could be of interest to the project's target groups.

Figure 7. DIGIECOQUARRY's dissemination assets

6.2 Dissemination and Communication materials and tools

DIGIECOQUARRY will produce a number of different Dissemination and Communication materials and tools that are deeply explained in D9.1 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan, in D9.2 DIGIECOQUARRY's website and in D9.3, D9.5, D9.8 Dissemination and Communication materials.

Although in deliverable D7.7 Communications with policy makers plan, the relationship between the materials developed for the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation and the Communication with policy makers Plan will explain the relation between the materials and the actions of communication with policy makers & public bodies, the most relevant ones for this purpose are listed below.

Identity of DIGIECOQUARRY

- Branding, graphical identity and templates.

Figure 8. DIGIECOQUARRY's Logo.

Promotional material

- Roll-up, leaflets, brochures, and posters.
- Infographics.

Publications

- Press releases.
- Online newsletter.
- Dissemination & communication articles in journals and magazines.
- Scientific publications.
- Public deliverables.
- Joint public-private publications coming from the project, from partners or from organisations outside the consortium.
- Letters.
- Specific reports or Executive Summaries.

Events

- Participation in scientific conferences.
- Participation in events, trade fairs and workshops (exhibitions, business events, information days, technical committees, assemblies, etc.).
- DIGIECOQUARRY's Workshops, seminars & panel presentations.
- DIGIECOQUARRY 's final conference.

On-line presence

- Project's website to foster the IQS platform & network with partners sites.
- Project's social media accounts & network with partners social media profiles.
- Blog & on-line Fora.
- Videos.
- Capacity Building Program (CBP) oriented to potential users and adopters.

Other channels & tools

- Partners communication channels.
- EU dissemination channels.
- Links & interactions with the exploitation plan.
- IP and knowledge management plan.
- Synergies with relevant projects and initiatives.
- Meetings with policy makers & public bodies (at EU, national, regional, local and international levels).
- Meetings with relevant related organisations (at EU, national, regional, local and international levels).
- Meetings with neighbourhood or community reference groups.
- Enquiries & surveys for citizens.
- Clustering actions (under WP8).
- Ensuring the development of the Gender Management Plan (under WP10).
- Templates for policy briefings.

Among the above, it is relevant for the purpose of this deliverable to enlarge the description of those more targeted for policy makers & public bodies:

6.2.1 Meetings with policy makers & public bodies (at EU, national, regional, local and international levels)

ANEFA and WP8 Leader (UPM-AI) will closely collaborate and coordinate the organisation of meetings with policy makers & public bodies at EU, national, regional, local and international levels to explain DIGIECOQUARRY and to interact with them to discuss potential issues and difficulties identified that could require political actions (policy, legislation or other).

The meetings will be organised, as appropriate, in face to face, online or hybrid modes, or even with visits to some of the pilot sites.

ANEFA and WP8 Leader (UPM-AI) will ask for partner's support for the organisation of some of the meetings and will coordinate the messages to align as much as possible the proposals.

ANEFA and WP8 Leader (UPM-AI) will promote active initiative from the other partners in order they will interact with their respective policy makers at national and regional levels.

The final list of meetings with policy makers at EU and national level will be reported in an updated version of the "DIGIECOQUARRY Communication and Dissemination Activities report" (deliverable D9.4).

6.2.2 Meetings with relevant related organisations (at EU, national, regional, local and international levels)

ANEFA and WP8 Leader (UPM-AI) will closely collaborate and coordinate the organisation of meetings with relevant related organisations (entrepreneur organisations, Trade Unions, Accademia, Technological Centres, NGOs, etc.) at EU, national, regional, local and international levels to explain DIGIECOQUARRY and to interact with them to discuss potential strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats identified that could require their collaboration or support.

The meetings will be organised, as appropriate, in face to face, online or hybrid modes, or even with visits to some of the pilot sites.

ANEFA and WP8 Leader (UPM-AI) will ask for partner's support for the organisation of some of the meetings and will coordinate the messages to align as much as possible the proposals.

ANEFA and WP8 Leader (UPM-AI) will promote active initiative from the other partners in order they will interact with their respective relevant related organisations at national and regional levels.

The final list of meetings with relevant related organisations at EU and national level will be reported in an updated version of the "DIGIECOQUARRY Communication and Dissemination Activities report" (deliverable D9.4).

6.2.3 Meetings with neighbourhood or community reference groups

Under WP7 it is foreseen to organise meetings at pilot site level with neighbourhood representatives or community reference groups to address social issues.

These meetings will be organised by WP7 leader, in coordination with ANEFA and representatives of pilot sites to better organise communication and dissemination actions related with.

The final list of meetings at pilot site level with neighbourhood representatives or community reference groups to address social issues will be reported in an updated version of the "DIGIECOQUARRY Communication and Dissemination Activities report" (deliverable D9.4).

6.2.4 Enquiries and surveys for citizens

Again, under WP7, it is foreseen to organise enquiries & surveys for citizens to address social issues.

These enquiries and surveys will be organised by WP7 leader, in coordination with ANEFA to better organise related communication and dissemination actions.

The final list of enquiries and surveys will be reported in an updated version of the “DIGIECOQUARRY Communication and Dissemination Activities report” (deliverable D9.4), and the main conclusions will be presented in deliverable 7.5 Social License to Operate.

6.3 Requirements for communication and dissemination materials and tools

Due to the complexity of the policy making process and the number of different groups involved, it can seem like an impossible task to work with policy makers to have an impact.

However, there are always windows of opportunity and strategies that can be employed to engage with policy makers, and improve the chances of having an impact.

That is why it is needed to plan effective ways of bringing DIGIECOQUARRY messages by preparing beforehand:

- WHO is the key policy maker or public body who has the power to make a difference?
- WHAT exactly is expected from policy makers to do?
- WHAT are the needs of policy makers?
- WHAT is the key message with relevance for policy?
- WHY is the proposal important for policy?
- HOW to deliver the messages? Short, clear and visual is best.
- WHEN to engage?
- WHERE to engage?
- HOW to engage?

In the preparation of the dissemination and communication materials, some recommendations have to be considered:

- Nice and clear graphic design and professional printing.
- Always keep it short. Prepare a summary / executive summary.
- Use images, tables, charts, infographics or other visual tools.
- Organise the information in:
 - Clear purposeful & powerful **title** that should state exactly what the communication is about.
 - **Presentation of DIGIECOQUARRY**. Summarise existing research, report project findings, present the organisation’s position.
 - **Key points**. Elevator pitch (2 minutes summary).
 - Brief and precise **introduction**.
 - **Findings** should be highlighted and take up most space but keeping it simple.
 - Clear, specific and realistic **policy recommendations**.

6.4 Requirements for meetings and workshops

For the organisation of meetings and workshops the requirements are:

- Find out the 'downtimes' for the targeted policy makers & public bodies.
- Organise short meetings that are best.
- Focus on audience's needs, on the relevant points for them, on the key messages and provide background information that could be needed.
- Prioritise dialogue, providing opportunities and chances to react, raise their concerns and provide their perspectives.
- Be prepared to listen to the perspectives of policy makers and answer questions about the relevance and quality of the proposals.
- Use appropriate and clear printed materials.

7 Ethical requirements for Communication

7.1 Context, governance, organisation and structure

7.1.1 Context

In addition to the general legislation, the extractive industry, in particular the aggregates sector, in which DIGIECOQUARRY operate, is subject to different specific national and international regulations.

Also, different Public bodies and associations and those linked to compliance regulations periodically issue standards and guides of conduct that must also be observed and taken into consideration, as references and best practices of the sector.

In addition, many DEQ partners have policies and internal regulations that regulate their daily activity and take into account the interests and needs of its main stakeholders.

That is why DEQ Consortium will comply in any case with the following requirements, regulations, standards and external legislation in force at all times, sector and locations in which the DEQ Consortium operates.

7.1.2 Governance, organisation and structure

The governance organisation and structure of the DEQ Consortium is described in the Figure 9.

Figure 9. DIGIECOQUARRY's organisational structure.

In relation with the communication with policy makers & public bodies, the roles are defined as follows:

- PCo | PROJECT COORDINATOR will be responsible for coordinating and centralising communication actions with policy makers & public bodies, organising meetings, monitoring compliance in the communication and ensuring smooth communications between partners and policy makers & public bodies.
- PMB | PROJECT MANAGEMENT BOARD will agree the details of the governance procedures to be used in the communication actions with policy makers & public bodies. Its main responsibilities are defining the overall strategy for the communication actions with policy makers & public bodies to be followed and deciding any modification of the work plan.

- PTC | PROJECT TECHNICAL COMMITTEE will prepare the content of the required materials for a smooth communication actions with policy makers & public bodies.
- IAB | INTERNATIONAL ADVISORY BOARD will play a key consulting role in the communication actions with policy makers & public bodies.

A new ETHICS ADVISORY BOARD – EAB will be established in the DEQ Consortium to advise on any ethical issue to be considered during the project and, in particular, in the communication actions with policy makers & public bodies. This EAB will be integrated by the PCo, the Ethics responsible of the project, a representative of ZABALA and a representative of the IAB, in that case an UEPG representative.

7.2 Ethics

Ethical aspects are in the center of DIGIECOQUARRY Project, and are considered from the very beginning and included in all the activities of the project. All Ethical issues are considered in the Deliverable D11.1 Ethics Requirements.

This Deliverable sets out the 'ethics requirements' that the DEQ project must comply with, explaining how the data is relevant and limited to the purposes of the research project. It provides information on identified challenges and summarises fundamental requirements to deal with ethical, privacy, data protection and other related issues in the project. It must be followed by all beneficiaries to ensure compliance with ethical and related requirements during and after the DEQ project.

In addition, national legislation must be considered if relevant requirements arise. The deliverable will help beneficiaries to comply with privacy policies and to decide if and for which actions external ethics approvals are necessary. If so, it also outlines the procedure for obtaining such an approval. Furthermore, to deal with such issues an Ethics Advisory Board (EAB) of the project is built including members with expertise on ethics. They will assist the project in identifying and solving ethical concerns that might not be identified by the end users or the project group. Members and responsibilities of the Ethics Advisory Board are also named in this document.

Figure 10. DIGIECOQUARRY's ethics principles for the communication with PM & PB.

7.2.1 Legal Background and Further Regulation

This section lists the main legal bases and other relevant directives and possible sources of information. Some of these are briefly summarised, others are merely listed as further readings. The sources listed here are to be understood as an indicative list. It is the responsibility of the individual actors within the project to identify and comply with relevant legal requirements for the planned activities.

The Ethics Advisory Board (EAB) of the project can provide support and advice in the process.

7.2.1.1 Horizon 2020 Regulations

As established in article 19 of Regulation (EU) No 1291/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of December 11, 2013, which regulates Horizon 2020 - the Framework Program for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) and repealing Decision No 1982/2006 / EC:

“All the research and innovation activities carried out under Horizon 2020 shall comply with ethical principles and relevant national, Union and international legislation, including the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and the European Convention on Human Rights and its Supplementary Protocols.

Particular attention shall be paid to the principle of proportionality, the right to privacy, the right to the protection of personal data, the right to the physical and mental integrity of a person, the right to non-discrimination and the need to ensure high levels of human health protection.”

7.2.1.2 EU Regulations and Guidelines

The most fundamental ethical requirements for research projects involving human participants at European level can be traced back to the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (CFR) and the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ECHR).

For privacy and the protection of personal data, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) forms the most important legal basis. In this context, the requirements of the Directive on privacy and electronic communications and Directive 2009/136/EC may also be relevant.

It is also of fundamental importance in the field of cybersecurity the Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013 (Cybersecurity Act).

As for data processing research, we should not forget to mention the Regulation (EC) 45/2001 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18, December 2000 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data by the Community institutions and bodies and on the free movement of such data, as well as the Directive 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2002 concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector and Directive 2006/24/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 March 2006 on the retention of data generated or processed in connection with the provision of publicly available electronic communications services or of public communications networks and amending Directive 2002/58/EC.

At this point, it is also important to mention Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), Ethical Guidelines for Good Research Practice, Guidelines on Automated individual decision-making and Profiling, the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, Ethics of Information and Communication Technologies, and Ethics Guidelines for trustworthy AI. More details on European data protection legislation are presented in the Handbook on European Data Protection Law.

7.2.1.3 International Guidelines and Codes of Conduct

Although science transcends national boundaries, except for research involving human subjects, there are no definitive international standards for research integrity.

To uphold ethical principles in research, the **Declaration of Helsinki** and the **Nuremberg Code** should always be complied with. Both documents contain important cornerstones to ensure ethics in research at an international level.

7.2.2 We should also mention the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the UNESCO Recommendation on the Status of Scientific Researchers of 20 November 1974; the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, New York (1966) and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, New York (1966). General Ethical Principles in the DEQ Grant Agreement

When implementing Horizon 2020 (H2020) funded projects, beneficiaries must act in accordance with ethical principles – this includes standards of research integrity – and applicable international EU and national laws. Article 34 of the H2020 - Grant Agreement (AGA) lists the following basic ethical principles that must be followed:

“The beneficiaries must carry out the action in compliance with: (a) ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity)

And (b) applicable international, EU and national law.

In addition, the beneficiaries must respect the fundamental principle of research integrity — as set out, for instance, in the European Code of Conduct for Research.

This implies compliance with the following fundamental principles:

- **reliability** in ensuring the quality of research reflected in the design, the methodology, the analysis, and the use of resources.
- **honesty** in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting, and communicating research in a transparent, fair, and unbiased way.
- **respect** for colleagues, research participants, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage, and the environment.
- **accountability** for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision, and mentoring, and for its wider impacts

and means that beneficiaries must ensure that persons carrying out research tasks follow the good research practices and refrain from the research integrity violations described in this Code.

This does not change the other obligations under this Agreement or obligations under applicable international, EU or national law, all of which still apply.”

Also, to be mentioned in this context are requirements for **gender equality** (Article 33), **avoidance or disclosure of conflicts of interest** (Article 35) and **confidentiality** (Article 36). The aspects mentioned here can also be found in the Grant Agreement No. 101003750 on this project.

Fundamental legal bases include the **Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union** (CFR) and the **European Convention on Human Rights** (ECHR).

7.2.3 Compliance with EU Transparency Register

As it has been explained in clause 4.3, eleven of the DIGIECOQUARRY Consortium members are registered in the EU Transparency Register⁴. Among them, ANEFA as PCo and as responsible of the communication with

⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/transparencyregister/public/homePage.do?redir=false&locale=en>

policy makers & public bodies, has to fully respect and comply with the requirements of the EU Transparency Register.

“EU Transparency Register is a complete framework at EU level that has been taken as a reference for the requirements for communication with policy makers & public bodies.

The EU institutions interact with a wide range of organisations and groups representing specific interests. This is a legitimate and necessary part of the decision-making process, ensuring EU policies reflect society’s real needs.

However, this process must be transparent, to allow for proper public scrutiny and ensure EU institutions are accountable to European citizens.

The more open the process, the easier it is to ensure balanced representation and avoid undue pressure or privileged access to information or decision-makers for certain parties.

This is why the European Parliament, the Council of the European Union and the European Commission have established the Transparency Register – to enact our commitment to openness about the groups and organisations that try to influence the formulation or implementation of EU policy and legislation.

The Transparency Register is a database listing ‘interest representatives’ (organisations, associations, groups and self-employed individuals) who carry out activities to influence the EU policy and decision-making process.

It is designed to show what interests are being represented at EU level, by whom and on whose behalf – and the resources devoted to such interest representation activities (including financial support, donations, sponsorship, etc.).

The Register has the following key features:

- A **public website** where interest representatives register up to date information about their activities at EU level.
- A **code of conduct** governing how interest representatives should interact with the EU institutions.
- A **complaints mechanism** to enable anyone to trigger an administrative inquiry into alleged cases of non-observance of the code of conduct by registered interest representatives”.

7.2.3.1 EU Transparency Register’s Code of Conduct

“Applicants are eligible to be entered in the Transparency Register if they follow certain ethical and behavioural principles in the course of their interest representation work with the EU institutions.

These principles are set out in a code of conduct annexed to the Interinstitutional Agreement and are summarised below. The code is a central part of the Transparency Register, ensuring that registrants act in line with its purpose and key objectives.

Observing the code is a necessary condition for registrants to remain in the Register.

Registrants must follow the rules and principles set out in Annex I of the Interinstitutional Agreement. In particular, they must:

- (a) in their relations with any of the signatory institutions and other Union institutions, bodies, offices or agencies (together referred to as ‘Union institutions’), always identify themselves by name, by registration number and by the entity or entities they work for or represent;

- (b) declare the interests and objectives they promote, and specify the clients or members whom they represent as well as, where applicable, the registration number of those clients or members;
- (c) not obtain or try to obtain information or decisions dishonestly or by use of undue pressure, improper behaviour or offensive language;
- (d) not abuse their registration for commercial gain or distort or misrepresent the effect of registration;
- (e) not damage the reputation of the register or cause prejudice to the Union institutions or use their logos without express authorisation;
- (f) ensure that the information that they provide upon registration, and subsequently administer in the framework of their covered activities, is complete, up-to-date, accurate and not misleading, and agree to that information being made available in the public domain;
- (g) respect, and avoid obstructing the implementation and application of, the relevant publicly available rules, codes and guidelines established by the Union institutions;
- (h) not induce Members of the European Parliament, members of the Commission or staff of the Union institutions to contravene the rules and standards of behaviour applicable to them;
- (i) if employing former Members of the European Parliament, members of the Commission or staff of the Union institutions, take the confidentiality requirements and rules applicable to those individuals after leaving the respective institution duly into account, with a view to preventing conflicts of interest;
- (j) where engaged in a client-intermediary relationship:
 - (i) ensure that the parties in such a relationship are entered in the register; and
 - (ii) as clients or intermediaries, ensure that the relevant information concerning the relationship entered in the register pursuant to Annex II is published;
- (k) where, for the purpose of carrying out covered activities, they outsource certain tasks to third parties that are not themselves registered, ensure that such parties adhere to ethical standards that are at least equivalent to those that apply to registrants;
- (l) present to the Secretariat, if requested, supporting material demonstrating their eligibility and the accuracy of the information submitted, and cooperate sincerely and constructively with the Secretariat;
- (m) acknowledge that they may be subject to the investigation procedures and, where applicable, measures provided for in Annex III;
- (n) take appropriate steps to ensure that any of their employees engaged in covered activities are informed about their commitment as registrants to observe this code of conduct;
- (o) inform the clients or members they represent in the framework of covered activities of their commitment as registrants to observe this code of conduct;
- (p) respect, and avoid obstructing, the specific access and security rules and arrangements established by the signatory institutions.

7.2.4 Complementary ethical principles to be applied

The ethical principles to be applied in the communication with policy makers and public bodies are based on the Society of European Affairs Professionals – SEAP Code of Conduct, taken as reference:

- **Transparency:** The information is essential for the development of activities of the DEQ Consortium, so transparency in its management must be the object of special protection and attention. The DEQ Consortium will act with transparency in the management of the entity, reporting its objectives, strategies, and activities to its members and to society in general. The relations with the EU network, Institutions, Stakeholders, and society will be raised under the principles of cooperation and transparency.
- **Independence:** in defence of the interests entrusted, the DEQ Consortium will act with full independence from any public entity, institution, political party or economic or social agent. The governing bodies of the association will base their decisions and agreements, solely and exclusively, in the general business interests whose defence they are entrusted with.
- **Accurate information:** The governing bodies of DEQ Consortium will guarantee that any policy makers & public bodies will receive detailed and transparent information. All the partners have a duty to pass on all necessary information, both internally and externally, truthfully, completely and in no case intentionally providing incorrect or inaccurate information that may lead to error to whoever receives it.
- **Compliance with the law and internal regulations:** Respect for the Law and Zero tolerance towards the commission of illicit acts constitutes a fundamental principle. All DEQ Consortium staff must comply, in the exercise of their professional functions and responsibilities, with current legislation and internal regulations applicable.
- **Compliance with antitrust and fair competition laws:** DEQ Consortium will act with full respect for free competition without, in any case, using the project to carry out collusive practices. DEQ Consortium will comply with antitrust and fair competition laws. Anticompetitive activity and the establishment of agreements to limit competition or gain an undue advantage is totally prohibited.
- **Institutional collaboration:** institutional collaboration is compatible with the independence of action with respect to the public powers and other economic and social agents. In accordance with the foregoing, the DEQ Consortium will maintain effective collaboration with as many Institutions, Bodies and Administrations as are necessary to achieve its objectives.
- **Anticorruption and antibribery:** The DEQ Consortium is against influencing the will of people to obtain any benefit using unethical practices. All DEQ Consortium responsables must act in accordance with the law and, in no case, may they carry out or tolerate bribes from or to third parties, for the purpose of unlawfully obtaining or maintaining business or advantages.
- **Conflicts of interest:** DEQ Consortium will always act prioritising the interests of the project over their own, those of their relatives or those of other linked people, both in the relationships they maintain with the policy makers & public bodies, as in those that they maintain with suppliers or any other third party. None of them may make a particular use of the DEQ Consortium assets, beyond that to which they are entitled, or make use of their position in the DEQ Consortium to obtain any advantage.
- **Protection and respect for the environment:** The DEQ Consortium assumes the need for protection and respect for the environment in accordance with the sustainability criteria and protection of biodiversity.
- **Healthy and safe work environment:** DEQ Consortium will promote the adoption of health and safety measures at work and will adopt the necessary preventive measures, promoting a work environment that respects the health and dignity of the employees of the industry.

- **Compliance with intellectual property policies:** DEQ Consortium have the duty to use the resources appropriately and responsibly. These resources must be protected and preserved from any misuse that could result in harm to employees and the DEQ Consortium.
- **Confidentiality:** All DEQ Consortium partners will keep secret the content of the deliberations that take place during their meetings with policy makers & public bodies and will refrain from revealing the information to which they have had access. The obligation to keep secrecy is permanent, so it will remain in force even after the termination occurs.
- **Compliance with privacy policies:** The DEQ Consortium respects the privacy of its employees, suppliers, partners and other interested parties. Consequently, the use of the information, whether personal or of another type, will comply with contractual obligations, privacy policies and applicable data protection.
- **Non-discrimination and equal opportunities:** The DEQ Consortium promote the professional and personal development of all its experts, ensuring equal opportunities. No type of discrimination is accepted in the professional sphere, among others, for sex, sexual orientation and identity, age, religion, political opinion, nationality, social origin, or disability reasons. People who hold management or command positions must act as facilitators of the professional development of their collaborators. A Gender Equality Plan would be developed within the DEQ Consortium to ensure the gender balance and equal opportunities within the project.
- **Democratic decision-making:** the DEQ Consortium bodies will operate in accordance with democratic principles. In addition, active participation of all those organisations, agents or stakeholders who may have a direct or indirect interest in the activities and procedures developed by the DEQ Consortium will be encouraged prior to the adoption of final decisions.

8 General better regulation requirements

Due to its European nature, DIGIECOQUARRY Project has to deal with EU policies and laws and also with those of the EU countries member of the Consortium and, finally with those of the other EU countries.

This means European + 27 Countries regulations.

Due to the heterogeneity of the national regulations and, even more, of what is considered as “better regulation” in each country, it is not possible to define a set of requirements for it, based on the evaluation of each individual case.

So, since DIGIECOQUARRY Project is EU founded, the requirements that will be applied for the better regulation approach are those defined by the European Commission⁵. These requirements will be used as a common ground for the communication with policy makers and public bodies at national, regional and local level, as well as at international level. When needed, the requirements will be adapted according to the specific circumstances.

The EC Better Regulation agenda ensures evidence-based and transparent EU law-making based on the views of those that may be affected. The Commission continuously evaluates and improves EU laws, focusing on delivering where it matters the most.

To foster Europe’s recovery, it is of key importance for the EC to legislate transparently and as efficiently as possible, based in the following principles:

- *“Removing obstacles and red tape that slow down investments and building of 21st century infrastructure, by working with Member States, regions and local level and key stakeholders*
- *Simplifying public consultations by introducing a single ‘Call for Evidence’, on the improved Have Your Say portal. This will generally combine the feedback on roadmaps and inception impact assessments with the questionnaire into one call for evidence.*
- *Introducing a ‘one in, one out’ approach, to minimise burdens for citizens and businesses by paying special attention to the implications and costs of applying legislation, especially for small and medium-sized enterprises. This principle ensures that any newly introduced burdens are offset by removing equivalent burdens in the same policy area.*
- *Mainstreaming the United Nations’ Sustainable Development Goals, to ensure that all legislative proposals contribute to the 2030 sustainable development agenda.*
- *Improving the way in which Better Regulation addresses and supports sustainability goals and the digital transformation.*
- *Integrating strategic foresight into policymaking to ensure it is fit for the future, by for instance, taking into account emerging megatrends in the green, digital, geopolitical and socio-economic contexts.”*

In that sense, DIGIECOQUARRY Project will communicate with policy makers and public bodies (EU, National, Regional, Local and International) by the following ways:

⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/law-making-process/planning-and-proposing-law/better-regulation-why-and-how_en

- **Sharing views and ideas:** *“The Commission has been seeking evidence and feedback from citizens, businesses, and stakeholders at all stages of the legislative and policymaking process since 2015. You can share your views and ideas on Commission initiatives across all policy areas on the [Have Your Say portal](#). It is possible to sign up for notifications regarding new developments as initiatives take shape, including after the adoption of legislation.”*

Furthermore, when needed, DIGIECOQUARRY Project will propose specific meetings (present, videoconferences, etc.) to share views and ideas. Invitations to Workshops or other plenary meetings will also be a communication option. And the preparation and dissemination of specific reports will also be a valuable tool.

- **Delivering contributions and proposals in consultation processes:** *“Contributions from citizens, businesses and stakeholders make a real difference to EU policies. They have guided and improved the Commission’s work on several important initiatives”.*
- **Proposing to simplify or adapt EU laws:** *“The Commission is assessing the performance of existing EU laws and making changes where necessary to keep them fit for purpose by:*
 - *The [Regulatory Fitness and Performance \(REFIT\) programme](#) was established in 2012 to make EU law simpler and to reduce unnecessary costs of regulation while still achieving benefits.*
 - *The [Fit for Future Platform](#) – a high-level expert group composed of representatives of Member States, the Committee of the Regions, the European Economic and Social Committee and stakeholders representing civil society, business and non-governmental organisations. The group assists the Commission in improving EU laws by providing opinions to the Commission on potential for simplification, burden reduction and modernisation opportunities of existing EU laws. Anyone can propose suggestions for the simplification of existing EU laws through the [Have Your Say: Simplify! portal](#)”.*
 - *[Evaluations and fitness checks](#) are used to assess whether EU laws, policies and funding programmes are delivering the expected results at minimum cost.”*

- **Strengthening subsidiarity and proportionality:** *“The principles of subsidiarity and proportionality are cornerstones of the EU treaties, and are systematically applied to the Commission’s legislative proposals.*

With the subsidiarity principle, the Commission aims to only act where it is necessary and where it delivers clear benefits over and above measures taken at national, regional or local levels. Except in cases where the EU has exclusive competence, action at European level should not be taken unless it is more effective than action taken at national, regional or local level. A subsidiarity grid is attached to all politically sensitive and important initiatives accompanied by an impact assessment.

Proportionality focuses on the financial and administrative impact of proposed legislation, to ensure that regulatory actions do not exceed what is necessary to achieve the legislative and policy objectives. Any such impact must be minimised and must be proportionate to the policy objectives. For the Commission this means delivering our ambitious policies in the simplest, least costly way, avoiding unnecessary red tape.”

- **The EU institutions working together:** *“Improving EU law-making is a shared objective and the responsibility of all EU institutions and Member States. The best way to improve EU law-making and deliver better results is for the European Parliament, the Council of the European Union and the European Commission to work more closely together in the coming years.*

Given the opportunities and challenges that lie ahead in our path to a sustainable recovery, it is crucial to legislate as efficiently as possible, with our future in mind. The effective application, implementation and enforcement of EU law is a priority for the von der Leyen Commission. The Commission can only determine the costs and savings associated with its own legislative proposals. Changes made during negotiations with the European Parliament and the Council may significantly alter impacts for people and business.”

- **International regulatory cooperation:** *“The EU is built on commonly agreed rules. For these rules to work, Member States must fully implement and enforce them in a timely fashion. They then need to ensure that the rules are correctly applied and enforced, because non-enforcement bears costs for citizens and businesses.*

The effective application, implementation and enforcement of EU law is a priority for the von der Leyen Commission. As announced in President von der Leyen’s political guidelines, the Commission will continue to guide and support Member States in their efforts to transpose directives, implement regulations and apply EU rules properly. Compliance checks verify how Member States translate EU legislation into national legislation. To ensure effective dialogue in the transposition phase, we depend on the Member States for clear and precise information on national legislation.

Going forward, the Commission intends to carry out a stocktaking of its oversight and enforcement activities, to ensure that they remain fit for making EU law work in practice.”

9 Specific political & regulatory framework for Communication

At this early stage of the development of DIGIECOQUARRY Project it is not possible to precisely identify what will be the specific needs that will require active communication with policy makers and public bodies (EU, National, Regional, Local and International).

Nevertheless, due to the scope of DIGIECOQUARRY Project, the specific regulatory framework for the communication with policy makers and public bodies at all levels, will be based on the interconnected topics and issues summarised in Figure 11 and Figure 12.

Figure 11. DIGIECOQUARRY's main political & regulatory framework for the communication with PM & PB.

Figure 12. DIGIECOQUARRY's detailed political & regulatory framework for the communication with PM & PB.

9.1 Green Deal & 2030 climate framework

The European Commission presented in December 2019 the European Green Deal – a roadmap for making the EU's economy sustainable by turning climate and environmental challenges into opportunities across all policy areas and making the transition just and inclusive for all. This is the core of the EU's environmental, climate and also industrial policy, setting out the target of climate-neutrality in 2050, zero pollution, and increasing the CO₂ reduction targets to 55% by 2030, compared to 1990 levels. Then, all 27 EU Member States committed to turning the EU into the first climate neutral continent by 2050.

The European Green Deal covers all sectors of the economy, notably transport, energy, buildings, and industries such as steel, extractive industry (aggregates) and chemicals, among others. *"The European Green Deal provides*

a roadmap with actions to boost the efficient use of resources by moving to a clean, circular economy and stop climate change, revert biodiversity loss and cut pollution.”

The DIGIECOQUARRY Project will follow the European Green Deal principles that will “*set the blueprint for this transformational change. It put in place the building blocks for the economy of tomorrow with landmark strategies on biodiversity, circular economy, zero pollution, sustainable and smart mobility, ... and many others*”.

DIGIECOQUARRY Project will include the “*necessary elements to track progress in the implementation of EU climate legislation and to support the shift to climate neutrality, including research, skills, industrial, competition and trade policies*”.

Under the Regulation on the Governance of the Energy Union and Climate Action, the EU has adopted integrated rules to ensure planning, monitoring and reporting of progress towards its 2030 climate and energy targets and its international commitments under the Paris Agreement. The Regulation also ensures that EU planning and reporting are synchronised with the ambition cycles under the Paris Agreement.

DIGIECOQUARRY Project aims to contribute to both EU and national energy and climate plans covering the five dimensions of the Energy Union:

- Decarbonisation (greenhouse gas reduction and renewables).
- Energy security.
- Energy efficiency.
- Internal energy market.
- Research, innovation and competitiveness.

9.2 EU principles for sustainable raw materials

The DIGIECOQUARRY Project will try to support the objective of the EU principles for sustainable raw materials, to align the understanding of sustainable raw materials extraction (from exploration to post-closure) and processing operations in the EU amongst Member States and define the general direction towards the SDGs.

Achieving the Green Deal objectives requires access to sustainable raw materials, in particular critical raw materials necessary for clean technologies, digital, space and defence applications, by diversifying supply from both primary and secondary sources.

ANEFA, the PCo is a member (on behalf of UEPG) of the EC Raw Materials Supply Group (RMSG including Member States, regional authorities, industry associations, civil society, social partners and research organisations) and the European Commission have developed and agreed upon a set of voluntary, non-mandatory EU principles for sustainable raw materials.

The DIGIECOQUARRY Project is based in these principles that will feed into an integrated approach to sustainable raw materials extraction and processing in Europe in terms of social, environmental and economic performance.

*“A main building block of the Critical Raw Materials Action Plan is about strengthening the sustainable and responsible domestic sourcing and processing of raw materials in the European Union where **public acceptance** is an important element. The EU principles for sustainable raw materials support this goal. They have been developed to reflect the practices that are followed within the European Union and that are expected to be applied also by new entrants to the market”.*

*“The objective of the EU principles for sustainable raw materials, is to align the understanding of sustainable raw materials extraction (from exploration to post-closure) and processing operations in the EU amongst Member States and define the **general direction towards the SDGs**. This will lead to a common European understanding on sustainability principles that can contribute to coherence amongst emerging certification and labelling schemes, and that existing practices, codes and standards are recognised”. For instance, DIGIECOQUARRY Project is going to build in this field.*

*“The principles should enable to **better communicate with the public** on the conditions under which **sustainable raw materials extraction and processing** takes place in Europe and increase public acceptance for this activity.*

*The principles will build upon existing EU legislation concerning sustainability, and refer to internationally agreed sustainable raw materials extraction and processing initiatives. The principles do not impose any obligations on the Member States or the industry. Development of **indicators** and certification is outside the scope of this action”.*

The EU principles for sustainable raw materials are founded on the goals and values of the EU as laid down in the EU Treaties. Among them, the following ones are of particular relevance for DIGIECOQUARRY Project:

- Sustainable development based on **balanced economic growth** and price stability, a **highly competitive market economy** with **full employment, social progress, and environmental protection**.
- Promote **scientific and technological progress**.
- Enhance economic, social and territorial cohesion and solidarity among EU countries.

The EU principles for sustainable raw materials and then DIGIECOQUARRY Project both have a clear social dimension (Human rights, engagement with communities of interest, employment, health and safety).

Sustainable raw materials extraction and processing:

- Support **human rights, communities and sound governance**.
- Support **Decent Work** for the workforce.
- **Comply with all laws and regulations in the EU**, including EU legislation as laid down in the EU Treaties.
- Constitute an essential building block for **sustainable value chains** that have a strategic importance for economic growth and the sustainability of Europe’s economy and society, including the **transition to climate neutrality and a digital economy** while complying with the principle of **do no significant harm** as stated in the European Green Deal.
- Apply **sound financial management**.
- Apply **sound environmental management practices**.
- Improve and promote **efficient energy use, support climate change mitigation and adaptation measures**.
- Includes **materials stewardship** and **contributes to the EU’s circular economy** where possible and within its responsibilities.

9.3 UN Sustainable Development Goals

The DIGIECOQUARRY Project interacts and contributes to most of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) included in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development adopted in September 2015 by the General Assembly

of United Nations. Building on the principle of “leaving no one behind”, the Agenda emphasizes a holistic approach to achieving sustainable development for all.

The DIGIECOQUARRY Project is designed to contribute to:

- Direct contribution:
 - GOAL 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure
 - GOAL 12: Responsible Consumption and Production
 - GOAL 13: Climate Action
 - GOAL 6: Clean Water and Sanitation
 - GOAL 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities
 - GOAL 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth
- Indirect contribution:
 - GOAL 1: No Poverty
 - GOAL 2: Zero Hunger
 - GOAL 3: Good Health and Well-being
 - GOAL 4: Quality Education
 - GOAL 5: Gender Equality
 - GOAL 7: Affordable and Clean Energy
 - GOAL 15: Life on Land
- Marginal contribution:
 - GOAL 10: Reduced Inequality
 - GOAL 14: Life Below Water
 - GOAL 16: Peace and Justice Strong Institutions
 - GOAL 17: Partnerships to achieve the Goal

9.4 EU Digital Policies

Due to its nature, the DIGIECOQUARRY Project fits into the European Digital Policies like Europe's Digital Decade that pursues a human-centric, sustainable vision for digital society throughout the digital decade to empower citizens and businesses. EC recognises that *“there are still many challenges associated with the digital transformation that need to be addressed during the digital decade. The EU must increase its strategic autonomy in tech and develop new rules and technologies to protect citizens from counterfeit products, cybertheft, and disinformation. Most importantly, the EU needs to address the digital divide”*.

European Digital Policies can also support the EU in meeting objectives in the European Green Deal.

The Communication ‘Digital Compass: The European Way for the Digital Decade’ set out digital ambitions for the next decade in the form of clear, concrete targets. The digital compass uses the 4 points of the compass to identify the main goals to reach over the next decade:

- A digitally skilled population and highly skilled digital professionals (ICT specialists, and basic digital skills).
- Secure and sustainable digital infrastructures (Connectivity, Data – Edge & Cloud, Computing capacity, ...)
- Digital transformation of businesses (Tech up-take with high number of companies using Cloud / AI / Big Data), innovators and late adopters – focusing SMEs to increase their level of digital intensity)
- Digitisation of public services (interlink with business).

DIGIECOQUARRY Project will interact with these key policy areas to ensure these goals are met and to deliver issues related with cloud computing, artificial intelligence, digital identities, data, infrastructure and services, cybersecurity, blockchain and connectivity.

9.5 Health & Safety

Health and safety at work is one of the areas where the EU has had the biggest impact – with a solid legal framework covering the maximum number of risks with the minimum number of regulations. Directive 89/391/EEC, the so-called occupational safety and health (OSH) “Framework Directive”, lays down the main principles to encourage improvements in the safety and health of workers at work. It guarantees minimum safety and health requirements throughout the European Union while Member States are allowed to maintain or establish more stringent measures.

The Framework Directive is accompanied by further directives focusing on specific aspects of safety and health at work, in particular Workplaces Directive and the Display Screen Equipment Directive. Together they form the fundamentals of European safety and health legislation.

The EU strategic framework on health and safety at work 2021-2027 - Occupational safety and health in a changing world of work – deals with EU Digital Transition: *“Digital technologies can provide workers, including workers with disabilities or older workers, and their employers with digitally enabled **solutions to support their health and wellbeing**. These technological advances can offer increased opportunities to **improve work-life balance for both women and men**, and support OSH implementation through **accessible tools**, awareness raising and **more efficient inspection**. **Robotisation**, the **use of artificial intelligence**, and the greater prevalence of **remote work** reduce the risks of dangerous tasks, such as those in highly contaminated areas like wastewater systems, landfills, or agricultural-fumigation areas. However, new technologies also pose a number of challenges due to both: (i) the increased irregularity in when and where work is performed; and (ii) the **risks related to new tools and machinery**.”*

DIGIECOQUARRY Project has H&S as one of the major work axes, so this will be on the basis of any development associated with the project.

10KPIs

KPIs will be developed in D7.7 (M20) for the management and evaluation of the impact of the communication with policy makers & public bodies Plan.

11 Timetable

A table with the name of the activity, the responsible partner and the 48 months of the project will be prepared and permanently updated, to organise and prioritise the communication with policy makers & public bodies Plan.

This table will be used as a management tool and updated when required.

12 Conclusions

This deliverable is the base for the preparation of the communication with policy makers & public bodies of the DIGIECOQUARRY project because it defines the requirements that will be needed for the elaboration of the Communications with policy makers plan.

This deliverable will be completed in month 20 (D7.7) with the Communications with policy makers plan and in months 36 (D7.8) and 48 (D7.9) with the Evaluation report for Communications with policy makers.

It provides meaningful information regarding the requirements for communication with policy makers & public bodies; It includes the structure of the deliverable as well as its scope, its relation to other tasks, activities and deliverables and the first description of the procedures for communication with policy makers.

The different objectives of the communication with policy makers & public bodies are explained.

The deliverable defines the partners' requirements & role in the communication with policy makers & public bodies strategy.

It develops the different categories of policy makers, regulators & public bodies at international, EU, National, Regional & Local levels.

The reference to Dissemination and Communication materials and tools is made to WP9 materials. The requirements for communication and dissemination materials and tools and for meetings and workshops are also defined.

The deliverable describes the context, governance, organisation and structure as well as ethics, it explains that the requirements that will be applied for the better regulation approach are those defined by the European Commission and refers to Green Deal & 2030 climate framework, EU principles for sustainable raw materials, UN Sustainable Development Goals, EU Digital Policies and Health & Safety.

13References

The following references have been used for the preparation of this deliverable:

- EU Horizon 2020 call.
- DIGIECOQUARRY Grant Agreement number 101003750.
- DIGIECOQUARRY Consortium Agreement.

WP8

- D8.1 Clustering plan.
- D8.2 Protocols to cooperate with RMIS and EURMKB.

WP9

- D9.1 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan.
- D9.2 DIGIECOQUARRY's website.
- D9.3 Dissemination and Communication Materials.

WP10

- D10.3 Risk management and contingency plan.

14 Annex I. Article 29 - Dissemination of results - Open access - Visibility of EU funding

14.1 Obligation to disseminate results (article 29.1)

Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must — as soon as possible — ‘disseminate’ its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium).

This does not change the obligation to protect results in Article 27, the confidentiality obligations in Article 36, the security obligations in Article 37 or the obligations to protect personal data in Article 39, all of which still apply.

A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give advance notice to the other beneficiaries of — unless agreed otherwise — at least 45 days, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.

Any other beneficiary may object within — unless agreed otherwise — 30 days of receiving notification if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the dissemination may not take place unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard these legitimate interests.

If a beneficiary intends not to protect its results, it may — under certain conditions (see Article 26.4.1 of the Grant Agreement) — need to formally notify the Agency before dissemination takes place.

14.2 Open access to scientific publications (article 29.2)

Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.

In particular, it must:

(a) as soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications.

Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.

(b) ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest:

(i) on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or

(ii) within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.

(c) ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”.
- the name of the action, acronym and grant number.
- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- a persistent identifier.

14.3 Open access to research data (article 29.3)

Not applicable.

14.4 Information on EU funding — Obligation and right to use the EU emblem (article 29.4)

Unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

- (a) display the EU emblem and
- (b) include the following text:

‘This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003750’.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Agency.

This does not however give them the right to exclusive use.

Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

14.5 Disclaimer excluding Agency responsibility (article 29.5)

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

14.6 Consequences of non-compliance (article 29.6)

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the grant may be reduced (see Article 43).

Such a breach may also lead to any of the other measures described in Chapter 6.

15Annex II. List of members of UEPG

Austria
FVSK
Fachverband der Stein- und keramischen Industrie Österreich
FVSK
Wiedner Hauptstraße 63
1045 - Wien

Phone : +43 590 900 35 31
Email : info@baustoffindustrie.at
Website :<http://www.baustoffindustrie.at>

Belgium
FEDIEX
Fédération de l'Industrie Extractive
FEDIEX
Rue Edouard Belin, 7
1435 - Mont-Saint-Guibert

Phone : +3225116173
Email : secretariat@fedieux.be
Website : <https://www.fedieux.be/>

Cyprus
CAPA
Cyprus Aggregates Producers Association
CAPA
Dali, Cyprus
P.O.Box 11112 2551 - Limassol

Phone : +357 22266920
Email : latouros@latouros.com
Website :<http://www.cyprusquarries.pro.cy>

Denmark
Danske Råstoffer
Danish Aggregates Association
Danske Råstoffer
Nordre Voldgade 106
box 2125 1358 - København

Danske Råstoffer

Phone : +45 72160269
Email : lmv@danskbyggeri.dk
Website :<https://www.danskindustri.dk/medlemsforeninger/danske-rastoffer/>

Estonia
AS Kunda Nordic
HeidelbergCement Group
AS Kunda Nordic
Jaama 2
44106 - Kunda

Phone : +372 32 29 900
Email : knc@knc.ee
Website : <https://www.knc.ee/en>

Finland
INFRA ry
Infra Contractors Association in Finland
INFRA ry
Eteläranta 10
FI-00130 - Helsinki

INFRA

Phone :
Email : info@infra.fi
Website : <http://infra.fi/>

France
UNPG
Union Nationale des Producteurs de Granulats
UNPG
16 bis boulevard Jean Jaurès, Clichy
92110 - Paris

Phone : 0612387270
Email : unpg@unicem.fr
Website : <https://www.unpg.fr/>

Germany
MIRO
Bundesverband Mineralische Rohstoffe e.V.
MIRO
Düsseldorfer Straße 50
47051 - Duisburg

Phone : +49 203 992 39 60
Email : info@bv-miro.org
Website : <http://www.bv-miro.org/>

Greece
Lafarge Béton Greece
LafargeHolcim Group
Lafarge Béton Greece
19.3 Km Markopoulou Avenue, Paiania
190 02 - Attica

Phone : +30 210 2898 111
Email : info.gr@lafarge.com
Website : <http://www.lafarge.gr>

Halyps Building Materials S.A
HeidelbergCement Group
Halyps Building Materials S.A
Keramideza area
19300 - Mandra

Phone : +30 210 5556221
Email :
Website : <http://www.halyps.gr/ENG>

Hungary
Magyar Bányászati Szövetség
Hungarian Mining Association
Magyar Bányászati Szövetség
Báthory street 7
1054 - Budapest

Phone : +36-30-9518-207
Email : mbsz@mabsz.hu
Website : <http://www.mabsz.hu/>

Ireland
ICF
Irish Concrete Federation
ICF
8 Newlands Business Park, Naas Road, Clondalkin
22 - Dublin

Phone : +353 1 464 0082
Email : info@irishconcrete.ie
Website : <https://www.irishconcrete.ie/>

Israel
Lime and Stone Production Company Ltd
Associate company with Readymix Industries
Lime and Stone Production Company Ltd
155, Bialik Street
5252346 - Ramat Gan

Phone : +972-3-7519464
Email : infocenter_israel@cemex.com
Website : <http://www.readymix.co.il/>

Italy
ANEPLA
Associazione Nazionale Estrattori Produttori Lapidei ed Affini
ANEPLA
Via Fontana 23
IT-20122 - Milano

Phone : +39255184325
Email : anepla@anepla.it
Website : <http://www.anepla.it/>

Norway
Norsk Bergindustri
Norwegian Mineral Industry
Norsk Bergindustri
Næringslivets hus Middelthuns gate 27
0368 - Oslo

Phone : +47 23 08 88 40
Email : epost@norskbergindustri.no
Website : <https://www.norskbergindustri.no/>

Luxembourg
CLOOS
Associate company member
CLOOS
33, Route De Belval
4001 - Esch-Sur-Alzette

Phone : +352 57 03 73 - 1
Email : info@cloos.lu
Website : <http://www.cloos.lu/index.php?lang=eng&c=>

Portugal
ANIET
National Association of Extractive and Manufacturing Industry
ANIET
Rua Júlio Dinis, 931 1.º Esquerdo
4050-327 - Porto

Phone : +351 22 609 66 99
Email : geral@aniet.pt
Website : <http://www.aniet.pt/pt/>

Netherlands
Cascade
Vereniging Zand en Grindproducenten
Cascade
Bezoekadres Steigerboom 8
5331 KA - Kerkrand

Phone : +31 (06) 22892334
Email : l.vandervoort@cascade-zandgrind.nl
Website : <https://www.cascade-zandgrind.nl/>

Romania
PPAM
Patronatul Producatorilor de Agregate Minerale din Romania
PPAM
Bd. Regina Elisabeta, Nr. 3
030167 - Bucharest

Phone : +407 40111870
Email : office@ppam.ro
Website : <http://ppam.ro/>

Slovakia
SZVK
Slovak Association of Aggregates Producers
SZVK
Osloboditeľov 66
040 17 - Košice

Phone : +41 31 326 26 26
Email : info@fskb.ch
Website : <http://www.fskb.ch>

Phone : 00421 908 774 075
Email : kancelariaszvkv@intas.sk
Website : <http://www.szvkv.sk/szvkv/>

Spain
FdA
Federación de Áridos (FdA)
FdA
Plaza de las Cortes, 5 -7º
28014 - Madrid

Turkey
E-MAK
Asphalt Plant
E-MAK
Yunuseli Mh. Yunuseli Bulvar 75
16165 - Osmangazi Bursa

Phone : + 90 224 248 90 71
Email : info@e-mak.com
Website : <https://e-mak.com/en>

Phone : +34 915 021 417
Email : anefa@aridos.org
Website : <https://aridos.info/>

Ukraine
TBG
Technobud Group
TBG
9, Mykhailo Hryshka Street, Kyiv, office 1
02072 - Kyiv

Sweden
SBMI
Swedish Aggregates Producers Association
SBMI
Storgatan 19
114 51 - Stockholm

Phone : +38 (044) 391 32 07
Email : office.kiev@technobudgroup.com
Website : <https://technobudgroup.com/en>

Phone : +46 8 76 26 225
Email : kansliet@sbmi.se
Website : <http://www.sbmi.se>

United Kingdom (UK)
MPA
Mineral Products Association
MPA
Gillingham House 38-44 Gillingham Street
SW1V 1HU - London

Switzerland
FSKB
Fachverband der Schweizerischen Kies- und Betonindustrie
FSKB
Schwanengasse 12 3011
3011 - Bern

Phone : +44 207 963 8000
Email : info@mineralproducts.org
Website : <http://www.mineralproducts.org/>

16Annex III. List of members of GAIN

Region: **Argentina**

Association: CEMINCOR
Website: <http://cemincor.org.ar>

Association: Cámara de la Piedra
Website: camaradelapiedra.org.ar

Region: **Australia**

Association: CCAA
Website: www.ccaa.com.au

Region: **Brazil**

Association: ANEPAC
Website: www.anepac.org.br

Region: **Canada**

Association: ASGA
Website: www.asga.ab.ca

Association: BCSSGA
Website: www.gravelbc.ca

Association: OSSGA
Website: www.ossga.com

Region: **Chile**

Association: (ARENEX is a producer)
Website: www.arenex.cl

Region: **China**

Association: CAA
Website: www.zgss.org.cn

Region: **Europe**

Association: UEPG
Website: www.uepg.eu

Region: **India**

Association: AMA
Website: None

Region: **Korea**

Association: Aggregates Association of Korea
Website: <http://www.aak.or.kr/>

Region: **Malaysia**

Association: MQA
Website: www.mqa.com.my

Region: **New Zealand**

Association: AQA
Website: www.aqa.org.nz

Region: **Colombia**

Association: ASOGRAVAS
Website: www.asogravas.org

Region: **India**

Association: MEAI
Website: <https://meai.co.in/>

Region: **Japan**

Association: JCSA
Website: www.saiseki.or.jp

Region: **Latin America**

Association: FIPA
Website: www.fiparidos.info

Region: **Mexico**

Association: ASEC
Website: www.asec.mx

Region: **South Africa**

Association: ASPASA
Website: www.aspasa.co.za

Region: **United Arab Emirates**

Association: Stevin Rock
Website: www.stevinrock.ae

Region: **USA**

Association: NSSGA
Website: www.nssga.org

17 Annex IV. List of members of FIPA

ARGENTINA

Cámara de la Piedra de la Provincia de Buenos Aires
Dirección: Sarmiento 347- 2° Piso Of. 11- (1041) Buenos Aires
Telefax : 4325- 5843
Email: info@camaradelapiedra.org.ar
Website: camaradelapiedra.org
FAP Federación Argentina de la Piedra

BRASIL

ANEPAC Associação Nacional das Entidades de Produtores de Agregados para Construção Civil
Dirección: Rua Itapeva, 378 - Cj. 131 - Cerqueira César
São Paulo/SP - CEP: 01332-000
Telefone/Fax: (11) 3171 0159
E-mail: anepac@anepac.org.br
Website: anepac.org.br

CHILE

Cementos Bio Bio
Dirección: Parcela 15 fundo Santa Filomena de Nos
San Bernardo, Santiago, Chile
Teléfono: 56 - 2 - 9406510
Website: cementosbiobio.cl

COLOMBIA

ASOGRAVAS Asociación Colombiana de Productores de Agregados Pétreos
Dirección: Cra. 17 No. 88-23 Of. 302 Bogotá
Teléfono: 6212504 - 6917493
Fax: 6212592
Website: <http://www.asogras.org>

COSTA RICA

Cámara Minera de Costa Rica A.C.I.M.A.
Asociación Cámara Costarricense de la Industria Minera y Afines
Holcim Costa Rica
Website: www.holcim.org

ESPAÑA

FdA Federación de Áridos
Dirección: Plaza de las Cortes, 5 - 7ª Planta. CP: 28014 Madrid
Teléfono: 0034 915522526
Fax: 0034 914344415
E-mail: secretariafda@aridos.info
Website: aridos.info

18 Annex V. List of representations with policy makers of ANEFA

18.1 Corporate Representations

18.1.1 NATIONAL

Federation of Aggregates - FdA

- Assembly
- Board of Directors
- General Management

Confederation of Extractive Industries of Industrial Rocks and Minerals -

COMINROC (via FdA)

- Executive Committee
- General Assembly
- General Secretariat

Spanish Confederation of Mineral Raw Materials Industries - PRIMIGEA (via FdA)

- Executive Committee
- General Assembly
- General Management

Spanish Confederation of Business Organisations - CEOE (via COMINROC)

- Assembly

Confederación Española de la Pequeña y Mediana Empresa - CEPYME (via COMINROC)

- Board of Directors
- General Assembly

Spanish Confederation of Associations of Manufacturers of Construction Products - CEPCO (via FdA)

- Assembly of the
- Board of Directors

Spanish Association for Standardisation - UNE and AENOR (via FdA)

- Assembly
- Board of Directors

Spanish Technological Platform for Concrete - PTEH (via FdA)

- Assembly
- Board of Directors

Multisectoral Platform Against Late Payment - PMCM

- Assembly
- Board of Directors
- Treasurer

Mining and Life Foundation

- Founding Member
- Trustee
- General Secretary
- Rocks and Minerals, Society and Life Project Committee
- Education Working Group
- Image and Outreach Working Group
- Public Relations Working Group
- Resource Optimisation and Coordination Working Group

18.1.2 INTERNATIONAL

European Union of Aggregates Producers - UEPG (via FdA)

- Executive Committee
- Assembly of Delegates

Iberoamerican Federation of Aggregates Producers - FIPA (via FdA)

- Board of Directors
- Assembly of Delegates
- Honorary Directorate General

Global Aggregates Information Network - GAIN (via FdA, UEPG and FIPA)

- Assembly
- Board of Directors

18.2 Institutional Representations

18.2.1 NATIONAL

Mining Safety Commission (MITERD) (via COMINROC)

- Standing Committee
- Plenary
- Working Groups

Working Group on Extractive Industries Wastes (MITERD)

18.2.2 INTERNATIONAL

European Union (via UEPG)

- Relations of the European Extractive Industry with the European Commission
- Representation to the EU Minerals Raw Materials Supply Group (via UEPG)
- Representation to the European Agency for Safety and Health at Work (EU)
- Chairmanship (2020) of the Extractive Industries Sectoral Social Dialogue Committee
- Member of the European Commission's Committee on Explosives for Civilian Use
- Member of the EU's Strategic Coordination Group on Water

18.3 Technical Representations

18.3.1 NATIONAL

COMINROC

- Legal Affairs Committee
- Sector Strategy Committee
- Working Group on Participatory Processes
- Working Group on Respirable Crystalline Silica
- Working Group on Natura 2000 and Biodiversity

CEOE (via COMINROC)

- Economy and Financial Policy Commission
- Social Dialogue and Employment Committee
- International Relations Committee
- European Union Committee
- Infrastructure and Urban Planning Committee
- Sustainable Development and Environment Committee
 - Climate Change Working Group
 - Energy and Climate Working Group
 - Circular Economy / Waste Working Group
 - Working Group on Water and Coastal Protection
 - Environmental Quality Working Group
 - REACH - CLP Working Group
 - Agenda 2030 Working Group
 - Sustainable Mobility Working Group
 - Natural Capital Working Group
- Research, Development and Innovation Committee
- Industry and Energy Committee
- Social Security and Occupational Risk Prevention Committee
- Tax Committee
- Corporate Social Responsibility Committee
- Internal Market Committee
- Legal Committee
- Competitiveness, Trade and Consumer Affairs Committee
- Committee on the Promotion of Entrepreneurship
- Transport and Logistics Committee

CEPCO (via FdA)

- Late Payment Working Group
- Industry 4.0 Working Group
- Internationalisation Working Group
- BIM Working Group
- Market Surveillance Working Group
- Public Procurement Working Group
- Environment and Sustainability Working Group
- AENOR Working Group - Quality
- Health and Safety at Work Working Group
- Working Group on Reduction of Administrative Burdens
- National Congress of Construction Products Working Group

Spanish Association of Structural Engineering - ACHE**Spanish Association for Standardisation - UNE and AENOR (via FdA)**

- Consultative Commission on Circular Economy
- Consultative Commission on Construction

Official Madariaga Laboratory (via COMINROC)

- Impartiality Committee

Eduardo Torroja Institute Members' Association - AMIET

- General Assembly
- Circular Economy Working Group

18.3.2 INTERNATIONAL

UEPG (via FdA)

- Health & Safety Committee (Chair)
- Technical Committee
- Environment Committee
- Economic Committee
- Biodiversity Task Force
- Communication and Public Relations Task Force
- Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation Task Force (Chair)
- Water Management Task Force (Chair)
- Task Force on Recycling
- Hazardous Substances and HWP Task Force
- Mining Waste Task Force
- Air Quality Task Force
- Task Force on Respirable Crystalline Silica (Chair)
- Task Force on Economic Instruments (Chair)
- Task Force on Enhanced Compliance and Enforcement (Chair)
- Representation to the Non-Energy Extractive Industry Panel - NEEIP
- Liaison with the European Federation of Explosives Manufacturers - FEEM
- Representation to the NEPSI Agreement

18.4 Standardisation

18.4.1 NATIONAL (UNE) (via FdA)

Committee CTN-146 "AGGREGATES".

- Secretariat

Committee CTN-41 "CONSTRUCTION".

- Member

Committee CTN-83 "CONCRETE"

- Member

Committee CTN-22 "MINING AND EXPLOSIVES"

- Member

- SC 1 Mineral raw materials

- SC 2 Mining equipment and techniques

- SC 3 Sustainable mining management (chair - via COMINROC)

Committee CTN-103 - "GEOTECHNOLOGY".

- Member

- SC5 "Earthmoving

Committee CTN-198 - "SUSTAINABILITY IN CONSTRUCTION".

- Member

Committee CTN-193 - "EVALUATION OF THE EMISSION OF HAZARDOUS SUBSTANCES FROM CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS".

- Member

Committee CTN-157 - "PROJECTS".

- Member of

- WG. 13 "Landscape impact studies

Committee CTN 073 - "NUCLEAR ENERGY, NUCLEAR TECHNOLOGIES AND RADIOLOGICAL PROTECTION".

- Member

- WG 01 "Natural radioactivity in indoor environments".

Committee CTN-323 - "CIRCULAR ECONOMICS".

- Member

Committee CTN-165 - "ETHICS, GOVERNANCE AND SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY OF ORGANISATIONS"

- Member

- SC5 Public Procurement

18.4.2 INTERNATIONAL

Committee CEN/TC-154 "Aggregates" (European Committee for Standardisation - CEN)

- Plenary

- Panel of Chairpersons

- Spanish Delegation (UNE) in all Subcommittees and WGs

- Secretariat WG 11 Railway Ballast